

GENDER REPRESENTATION AND MULTI-PARTNER FERTILITY: A SOCIAL CONSTRUCTIVIST VIEW OF 'A TRIBE CALLED JUDAH'

Olowoniyi Funke Amanda

Elizade University, Ilara- Mokin

Ondo State, Nigeria

Email: olowoniyiamanda@gmail.com

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Abstract

In international relations, films have become mirrors through which we view the world and examine social narratives or phenomena in the global arena. While polygamy and polyandry are common in some parts of Africa, Multi-Partner Fertility (MPF) was linked to widowhood and remarriage; the practice of unmarried females having children by different men was uncommon and frowned upon. Nigeria ranks 11th position among countries with the highest adolescent pregnancy globally. The economic, security, health and social hazards of MPF raise concern for Nigeria's rising youth population. Consequently, this study examines the nexus between adolescent pregnancy and female multi-partner fertility in Nigeria. It interrogates how 'A Tribe Called Judah' depicts the concept of female multi-partner fertility from a global perspective. The exploratory research method and social constructivist theory of international relations were adopted. The findings reveal that the mismanagement of adolescent pregnancy, early sexual debut and societal norms further female multi-partner fertility by placing socio-cultural and religious perception above the needs of teenage mothers, thereby catalysing broader societal problems like crime, family disintegration, alcoholism and depression. The study recommends that international organisations like UNFPA, WHO, and UNICEF place emphasis on postnatal counselling for unplanned teen pregnancies at first birth and extend sexual reproductive health education to religious centres and middle-income areas using the most relatable medium.

Keywords: Gender Representation, Films, Multi-Partner Fertility, Adolescent Pregnancy, A Tribe Called Judah

Introduction

The use of popular arts or films in explaining concepts in international relations is familiar, as films have become mirrors through which we see the globe, a simulation between concepts and theories in interpreting global interactions. The use of film in international relations is moving beyond the margins as empirical data has shown that it is more engaging than textbooks, significantly when concepts are clarified and prioritised, as it brings themes in global affairs to the fore and exudes debates, leaving a more lasting impact on students (Brandon, 2011), Stefan and Alexander (2009) highlight four ways of using film in international relations: to depict historical events, to discuss particular subjects in global politics, to examine social narratives or phenomena in the global arena, and to explicate and analyse theories of international relations.

Multiple-partner fertility refers to a situation where a female parent has children with different fathers; it is the possibility of a mother having children with more than one partner (Guzzo, 2014; Carlson & Fursten Burg, 2006). Dorius (2011) captures MPF as the multiple-father family structure, establishing that multi-partner fertility is highest among Black women in the United States of America. Brinig and Garrison (2019), in an empirical study, identified key factors associated with MPF, including parental age, marital status, socioeconomic status, and ineffective parenting. These factors align with the challenges depicted in the film "A Tribe Called Judah"(2023), which includes poverty, drug use, and delinquency.

Fomby and Osborne (2017) view MPF as one of the multifaceted and dynamic nature of modern-day family structure reaction to the increasing rates of divorce, remarriage, and prevalence of childbirth among cohabiting singles. DeRose (2019), on the other hand, opines that MPF makes children vulnerable to poverty as most MPF mothers are situationally conditioned to a low economic status with less social support, contributing to aggressive behaviour and school detachment among MPF children; the study recommends that MPF is a significant factor to push for delayed parenthood.

Candida (2021), in a study on the causes of male multi-partner fertility in Uganda, identifies the age of first sex, number of sex partners, number of wives (polygamy), religion, and demography, among other factors, as the significant determinants of multi-partner fertility. While polygamy is widely practised in Africa, polyandry, that is, a woman having more than one partner, is uncommon and frowned upon, even in contemporary Nigeria. However, historically, polyandry was common among the *Irigwe* females in Northern Nigeria. However, this practice was outlawed in 1968, furthered by the Marriage Act of 2004, which makes it illegal for a married woman to contract another marriage (Adedayo, 2023; Akinyoade, 2019). So, multi-partner fertility, as used in this study, focuses on single female parents.

Yaya and Bishwajit (2018), using a regression model analysis in a study on multiple sexual partnerships among women in Nigeria, observed that there is an increase in the number of females who are sexually active before the age of 15, thereby increasing the possibility of multiple sexual partners and their exposure to sexually transmitted diseases. The study recommends intervention programmes to encourage the postponement of early sexual debut. Sethosa (2007), in a survey of teen pregnancy in South Africa, establishes poverty as a significant contributor to the menace, which consequently increases the number of school dropouts, unemployment, and a vicious cycle of poverty. Hence, the factors and indicators that further MPF are a reality in contemporary Nigerian society, but for the paucity of literature and data on them, it has become imperative to look at MPF, particularly female MPF, from the lens of the Nigerian society to determine its impact on gender issues and development.

The concept of MPF is yet to be embraced as a core objective of international organizations active in the realm of international relations. However, MPF has strong relationships with major themes like the issues of teen pregnancies, the case of the girl-child, infant mortality, **SDG Goal 3**, human development and security, particularly the increased rate of crime among youth. The USA appears to lead the research on this phenomenon due to a growing deficiency in socioeconomic position and increasing gap in education, crime, poverty and risky behaviours in children from MPF family structures (Brinig & Garrison, 2019). Most noteworthy is MPF's impending threat to increase and heighten the several dangers that children born into poverty are confronted with. Also, Guzzo (2014) observed that the complexity of family structure presented by MPF presents a major hurdle for public policy as regards child welfare, support and delinquent behaviours. Dorius and Guzzo (2013) reveal that MPF is a major predictor of both drug use and early sexual debut. Ginther, Grasdahl and Pollard (2021) showed that Adolescents linked with MPF families have a higher tendency than other children to drop out of secondary school and are unlikely to obtain a first degree. These, among other factors, have made the phenomenon (MPF) one of national concern and an area that international organizations like UNICEF and UNFPA need to look into.

The film, 'A Tribe Called Judah (2023)' captures critical issues within the context and framework of gender issues in international relations; it addresses matters surrounding the girl-child, teenage pregnancy, sex education, gender-based violence, stigmatisation, the feminisation of poverty, the dilemma of single motherhood, illiteracy, out-of-school children, unemployment, and the struggles of being a child and at the same time a mother. Adolescence pregnancy is an international issue but pervasive in developing countries; there are two sides to unplanned pregnancy prevention among adolescents. While one school of thought advocates for contraceptives, the other pushes for abstinence and delayed sex.

According to the WHO Fact Sheet (2023), as of 2019, teens between the ages of 15-19 had an estimated number of over 10 million unplanned pregnancies, 55% of which ended in abortion. Managing and preventing unplanned teen pregnancies is vital to achieving SDG Goal 3 (Ensure Healthy lives and promote wellbeing for all ages). While the rate of adolescent births globally is reducing, the number of childbirths to adolescents continues to increase, with the highest in sub-Saharan Africa. The United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) and the Action for Adolescent Girls programme have evolved several strategies to manage the incidence of adolescent pregnancies through investment in girls' education, providing an all-inclusive sexual education to young people, empowering girls and collaborating with communities to end child marriage (Olowoniyi et al., 2023). Nonetheless, the menace persists.

One of the significant contributors to MPF globally is maternal age at first birth. This, more than other factors, has been attributed to being a substantial cause of MPF. Among single females, unplanned teen pregnancy is a significant factor due to early sexual debut, peer pressure, socio-economic reasons, inadequate knowledge of sex education, cultural and religious perception against contraceptives, and reoccurring pregnancies, among other factors (Olorunsaiye, et al., 2021; Yaya & Bishwajit, 2018; Fomby & Osborne, 2018).

The character and phenomenon as portrayed by the protagonist (Jedidah) are assumed to be a Nigerian issue rather than a global issue, with critiques adducing the peculiarity of the protagonist's (Jedidah Judah) situation to fit only within the Nigerian societal context (Ali, 2024). Nevertheless, this is due to the little understanding and dearth of literature on female multiple partner fertility in Africa. The film eclipses a consequence or output of the mismanagement of adolescent pregnancy due to social-cultural taboos and social prestige embedded in the garb of religion, which places societal perception above the need of adolescent mothers, as the protagonist's first pregnancy at 17 was attributed to "young love". Rather than addressing and managing the root of the problem, the victim is left at the mercy of society, reflecting the communal position on teenage pregnancy despite decades of work by national and international organisations. Consequently, this led to a series of pregnancies and widowhood at 22, culminating in a 'multiple father family structure' or 'zero father family structure', leading to more significant societal problems like crime, thuggery, alcoholism, poverty, and mental health issues.

Although there are many works on adolescent pregnancy in Nigeria and its effects, there is a dearth of literature on its nexus to MPF and the consequent social hazard birthed by it, especially for a country with a large youth population. Lessons can be derived from the dynamics of MPF in the film, 'A Tribe Called Judah' within the context of social constructivism. This paper is initiated to fill this gap in knowledge. Thus, the following questions become pertinent: How does 'A Tribe Called Judah' depict the causal factors of female multiple-partner fertility? What is the nexus between the mismanagement of Adolescent pregnancy and female multi-partner fertility in Nigeria? The qualitative study relies on secondary data sources: film and peer-reviewed journals on public health, international relations, political science, and sociology.

Objectives of the Study

1. Examine the nexus between adolescent pregnancy and female multi-partner fertility in Nigeria.
2. Interrogate how 'A Tribe Called Judah' depict the concept of female multi-partner fertility from a global perspective.

Literature Review

Concept of Adolescence Pregnancy

Adolescent pregnancy is described as the incidence of pregnancy among girls between the age of 10-19, which may be intended or unintended. (Olowoniyi, et al, 2023). Adolescent pregnancy can occur within or outside marriage. It is estimated that in Africa, 20% of adolescent girls become pregnant, primarily due to inadequate or lack of information on sexual reproductive health issues. This lack of information can stem from various factors, including parental attitudes, demographic location (rural areas), single-parent households, illiteracy, and poverty (Kassa, 2010; Olowoniyi, et al., 2023). Significantly, socio-cultural values and opinions buttressed by religion and the disposition of health workers limit the use of contraceptives by teen mothers in most parts of Africa, leading to a surge in the number of unintended or unwanted pregnancies.

Shallon et al. (2021) link 46% of unplanned pregnancies among teens in Africa to bottlenecks in accessing contraceptives. Sidibe (2022) affirms that socio-cultural norms in Africa and disapproval of pre-marital sexual relations explain the hesitancy of health providers in administering contraceptives to teens and youths. Thus, despite efforts by national, international, and non-governmental organisations to tackle the challenge of adolescent pregnancy, encumbrances within society continue to limit these efforts. Complications during pregnancy and childbirth are the second cause of death in 15-19 years' females globally (Fergus et al., 2013).

Management of Adolescent Pregnancy

The global impact of adolescent pregnancy has made its management a matter of great concern. The Management of teen pregnancies cuts across the family unit, school, primary health care centres, religious organisations, the government and other national and international organisations. Comprehensive sex education should be included in school curricula to educate teenagers on sexual reproductive health, unsafe sex, contraceptives and pregnancies. For teens who are already pregnant, initiating a multidisciplinary team early to inform teens and their parents about prenatal and postnatal care is valuable as it equips them with the correct information for safe and unsafe abortions and care both for the teens and their parents (McCarthy, O'Brien, & Kenny, 2014). Additionally, long-lasting and easily reversible contraceptives (LARC) should be prescribed to prevent the recurrence of pregnancy.

Notably, the Management of adolescent pregnancy extends to two levels: prenatal and postnatal care (PNC); the latter appears to be more challenging due to inadequate resources and lack of access to PNC services, absence of information and awareness regarding existing services, stigmatisation, shame, and judgmental attitude from health workers and the public, fear of being stereotyped as irresponsible, and suitable psychosocial support (Javadi et al., 2023). The Raising Children Net Australia (2023) aver that parents of teen mothers should speak with a psychologist or counsellor to manage their feelings of anger, shock, disappointment, anxiety, blame game, and guilt as these feelings often wane over time.

Malek, Abdul-Razak, Hassan, and Othman (2019) assert that due to the peculiarity of teen mothers, a combined team of primary care doctors, nurses, counsellors, social workers, psychiatrists, paediatricians, and obstetricians is required to manage pregnancy, especially if it is unintended and unplanned. Also, the medical team must be trained on acceptable guidelines and policies, particularly regarding the ethics and norms in society.

Likewise, poor communication skills, between pregnant teens and their parents, is another form of mismanagement leading to heightened emotions, tension and psychological distress within the family, thereby increasing the potential health risk to the mother. Scholars (Malek et al., 2019; Aziato et al., 2016; Osaikhuwuomwan & Osemwenkha, 2013; Harrison et al., 2017; Maravilla et al., 2017; and Bruce, 2016) agree that unplanned adolescent pregnancy requires

efficient communication skills, empathy to garner trust from the victim and enhanced cooperation to provide continual reproductive health care as these have been proven to be effective in decreasing repeated pregnancies.

Multi-Partner Fertility: Issues and Analysis

Multi-partner fertility (MPF) is the likelihood or prospect of a biological parent having children with more than one partner (Guzzo, 2014). MPF is associated with the system whereby a woman or man has natural children with more than one partner. (Candia and Kisangale, 2021). Multi-partner fertility is defined as a parent's exposure to having children with other than one partner in the course of their existence (Fomby & Osborne, 2018). Researchers like (Guzzo, 2014; Candia and Kisangala, 2021; Dorius and Guzzo, 2013; Fomby and Osborne, 2017) have attributed the cause of multi-partner fertility to increased pre-marital sex, cohabitation, unplanned pregnancy, growing family instability, declining rates of marriages, widowhood and divorce.

There are different types of multi partner fertility, they include male or female multi partner fertility, multi partner fertility within a household or with single parent either the mother or father, multi partner fertility within marriage, that is, polygamy or polyandry, and multi partner fertility due to divorce or widowhood. (Guzzo, 2014; and Candia and Kisangale, 2021). Although the frequency of MPF is higher among low-income women, it is surprisingly common at all levels of education and income (Dorius, 2011). This study focuses on multi-partner fertility among females between 10-19 years' old who are currently single parents either due to first-time unplanned pregnancy or widowhood.

Multi-partner fertility has been described as an intricate issue with communal, national and social consequences due to the negative impact on the children. Negative impacts such as crime, drug abuse and other risky behaviours; the effects on the teen mother, such as mental health issues, dropout from school leading to increased illiteracy rate, unemployment, poverty, depression and alcoholism (Dorius and Guzzo, 2013; Fomby and Osborne, 2017; Guzzo 2014). These factors result in an increased crime rate in society, demanding an increased national budget in defence to manage crimes and delinquent behaviours and in more developed countries to provide social services. For instance, the USA spends annually 101 million dollars through the Office of Population Affairs and Teen Pregnancy Prevention Program (Office of Population Affairs 2023).

Although the concept of MPF is not new, the prevalence of MPF is making it a global issue due to its capacity to impact a nation's human development index, human capital index, and national security, as illiteracy, unemployment and poverty are intertwined (Martinez & Fernandez, 2010; Corral et al., 2021; Dorius & Guzzo, 2013; Orehero, 2019).

Theoretical Framework

Social Constructivism Theory

The theory of social constructivism was accentuated in core international relations by Nicholas Onuf in the late 19th century and Alexander Wendt. It hinges on the premise that international relations are not only influenced by political authority but also by a continual process of interaction and social practice. According to Fearnon and Wendt (2002), constructivism is centered on the causal explanation for phenomena and the analysis of how they are constituted. Barnett (2018) avers that critical areas of international relations are motivated by analytical and logical factors, primarily when these factors are jointly held and influence the interests and identities of the people.

Social constructivism asserts that people within a society establish the realities of their identity and interest via an active process of social interaction, ideas, norms and social definition. Thus, the cultural interpretation given by people and state actors to matters is a significant feature of constructivism. Constructivists classify social norms into three;

Normative Behaviour: To an extent, standards affect behaviour and conduct within a community.

Normative Emergence: the way an idea gains intersubjectivity within a community.

Socialisation: how an active norm from one society spreads and is internalised by external actors.

Social constructivists argue that identity is not fixed or static; instead, it is derived through the interactions of the global community (Prabhu, 2022). International organisations advance social constructivism by shaping the perceptions and interests of various actors. Social constructivism theory can be employed to understand and interpret the multiple aspects of the protagonist's action in the film, 'A Tribe Called Judah (2023)', which encompass teenage pregnancy, early first sex, inadequate sex education, poor management of adolescent pregnancy, the nexus between religion, parenting and societal norms, stigmatisation, and female multi-partner fertility.

The three social norms of social constructivism reflect the global perspective of female multi-partner fertility, which is more harmful than positive due to its social, economic and security impact on a nation. It further affirms that the path of life demonstrated by the protagonist sits well or fits into the concept of female multi-partner fertility, which is a global phenomenon and not a national or African issue as perceived by the general public.

Methodology

Presentation /Analysis of data

'A Tribe Called Judah' (2023): A Review

Films can be used as an empirical case study, making challenging concepts more concrete and understandable (Engert & Spencer, 2009). The character of Jedidiah Judah represents a teenager, a mother, a wife, a widow, and a victim of female multiple-partner fertility. Jedidiah gets pregnant at the young age of 17, which is attributed to "young love". Young love is a crush, infatuation, or first love associated with changes in puberty, teen hormones and behaviour, and the incomplete development of the adolescent prefrontal cortex (Simpson, 2019; Faith, n.d. & Newport Academy, 2024). Simpson (2019) avers that young love is not just a feature of puberty, as it must be triggered by someone or something.

Disowned by her father due to shame and societal expectations of a clergy's daughter, she moved to Kano to live with her maternal aunt, where she had her first child at 17 years old. At the age of 19, she had her second child, Adamu, but due to tribalism, religion, and the status of being a single mother, she was rejected by the family of the young man who impregnated her. She had her third child at 22 and was legally married to the father but became a widow at 23 at his death. To give her three sons a father figure, she married her children's lesson teacher and had her fourth son at 25. Unfortunately, he absconded with all her late husband left for her after she gave birth, and an investigation revealed he was married and had a family in another part of the country. This led to an emotional breakdown and depression; Jedidiah turned to alcohol as a coping mechanism to manage this phase of her life, leading to a fifth pregnancy and another son via a one-night stand at the beer parlour, "*a most shameful experience*" in her words. Most notable is the fact that Jedidiah's five sons were fathered by five different men from five different regions of Nigeria, heightening the perception of her being a loose woman, leading to mockery and the name tag of "WAZOBIA".

Dorius (2013), in an empirical study on maternal multi-partner fertility, posits that the phenomenon must be critically examined due to its pervasiveness and impact on a nation's children, mothers, and socio-economy. The study asserts that females who have children with multiple fathers have a higher percentage of underemployment, low wages, being less educated, and a higher chance of being disadvantaged throughout their whole life. This aligns with the condition of the protagonist, Jedidah, who had limited education because she dropped out of school after getting pregnant at 17 years and continued to struggle despite her hard work. Jedidah's character affirms Dorius (2013) position that MPF women spend six years more in poverty during their adult life compared to others.

Conversely, Burton (2011) observes that most studies on female multi-partner fertility are unbalanced as they blame the women for their circumstances without examining the reasons for their decisions and neglect the roles of the supposed fathers in contributing to the women's situation of multiple-partner fertility. Also, the mother is blamed for the plight of the children and the outcome of their negative behaviours. This is in line with the circumstances of Jedidah, who attempts to explain to another character (Mummy Micheal) that she did not intentionally set out to have children by different fathers after the latter's husband mocked and shamed Jedidah publicly for having children with various men. Burton (2011) contends that studies on MPF must take into consideration that MPF for some women is unplanned and is linked to domestic violence, failed relationships, or financial hardship. This is a representation of Jedidah's situation – from an unplanned teenage pregnancy to a reoccurring pregnancy, to widowhood, to a quest to satisfy the societal expectation of raising children with both parents, to being duped, and finding succour in alcohol, which only aggravated her anguish and trauma - a series of misfortune, completely unplanned.

Dr. Jeff Gardere, as cited in Crump (2011), avers that in ancient times, multiple fathers were an outcome of racism and poverty, especially among African Americans, with dire consequences for children from such unions. However, contrary to the position of scholars (Fomby and Osborne, 2017; Guzzo, 2014), he asserts that children from multi-partner fertility can still turn out well, this is evident in the case of Jedidah's two eldest children, Emeka and Adamu, until the mothers' condition pushed them into robbery. In contemporary times, Dr. Jeff Gardere traces MPF to increased divorce rates, a decreasing marriage rate, and fewer men willing to take responsibility for a family. For Jeff Gardere, the concept of MPF or multi-father family structure is an attempt to put an optimistic spin on the result of this kind of study, as in reality, most of these children are not only being raised with many fathers but without fathers (Crump, 2011).

Dorius (2011) and Formby and Osborne (2017), in an empirical study, observe five characteristics of MPF: it is linked to childbirth at an early age; unstable relationships; increases with the birth of each additional child but reduces with women who had their first child at an older age; children from MPF are likely to exhibit risky behaviours, and MPF is associated with persistent stressors like increased poverty, depression, low education, and underemployment. The film, 'A Tribe called Judah' validates all of these characteristics.

Nexus between Adolescent pregnancy and Female Multi-Partner Fertility

Nigeria ranks 11th position in adolescent pregnancies globally, which is linked to the high ratio of child marriage (Nigeria Spotlight Initiative, 2022; Musa et al., 2021). Adolescent pregnancy in Nigeria is one of the significant contributors to maternal and infant mortality, sexually transmitted diseases and abortion (Olorunsaiye et al., 2022; Okoli et al., 2022). Early commencement of sex, inadequate knowledge of sexual reproductive health and contraceptives, financial insecurity, early menstruation, unstable family structure, illiteracy and decline in African traditional values have been linked to the increased rate of unplanned adolescent pregnancy (Somefun & Olamijuwon, 2022). According to Dhimi et al. (2021), babies born to teenage mothers have worse health challenges than those born to older women despite the collaborative effort of national and international organisations to improve child survival and well-being.

Nonetheless, there are limited studies on how the management of adolescent pregnancy contributes to its surge in Nigeria, and there is no study on its influence on female multi-partner fertility in Nigeria or Africa due to poor record keeping and inadequate data.

Guzzo (2014) establishes that there is a higher likelihood of multi-partner fertility among adolescent females who have their first child unplanned and outside wedlock. Yaya and Bishwajit (2018), in an empirical study on multiple sexual partners in Nigeria using the Nigerian Demographic and Health Survey, affirm the position of (Guzzo, 2014) that early sex initiation is linked to MPF. Their study revealed that 28 percent of teenagers in Nigeria are having sex, with the female having their first sex earlier than 15 years. Yaya and Bishwajit (2018) link multiple sexual partners among female teens to inadequate sexual and reproductive health information, poor women empowerment, peer pressure, and misinformation on sexual testing to determine future partner compatibility. All these encompass mismanagement because with sufficient details, teen pregnancy can be avoided, and even when it happens, the reoccurrence can be prevented. However, a lack of information on comprehensive sexuality education from parents or guardians, schools, or religious institutions at the proper time due to cultural constraints, ignorance, myths, and assumptions furthers multiple sexuality partners and, consequently, MPF (Skay, 2021).

Furthermore, Folayan, Odetoynbo, Brown, and Harrison (2014) aver that one of the primary reasons for early sexual activity among teens in Nigeria is purported 'love', followed by peer pressure. This aligns with the situation of the protagonist (Jedidiah) in 'A Tribe Called Judah', who attributed her first pregnancy to "young love". Who is responsible for teaching a teen about love? The response to this question is in Auguste Comte and Herbert Spencer's structural functionalism theory, which views society as a composite system or organ whose segments function together to advance stability and solidarity (Macions, 2011). Parents, school, and religious institutions all have a role to play. Fagell (2016) posit that relationship tenets must be taught intentionally and that if parents do not teach children about love, the media and external influences would.

Whitney (2016) argues that the school, through its influences, partly raises the child. McGeady (1998) asserts that the faith community, whether the church, mosque or synagogue, is a vital organ in any community or nation and outlines five reasons it should be involved in teen pregnancy prevention: its focus on values, community credibility, access to teens, parents, teachers, and volunteers; skills in conflict resolution (in cases of a postnatal situation), and willingness to provide in-kind contributions. Sutrisno *et al.* (2021), using a statistical regression analysis, examine Christian religious education toward teenagers' character building; the finding reveals that 49% of teens' characters were influenced by Christian religious education; the study identifies that parental education, teacher's knowledge, media and social environment play a significant role too. Thus, a gap in these areas contributes to the character and manifestation of behaviour among teens. However, the faith community's position, as explained by McGeady (1998), was not demonstrated by Jedidiah's father, a clergyman in the film, 'A Tribe Called Judah (2023)'.

Parenting and the Prevention of Adolescent Pregnancy

Dorius (2013) establishes a connection between multi-partner fertility, poor parenting behaviour, family instability and socio-economic disadvantage. While the concept of parenting varies across cultures and societies, emotional abuse, neglect, physical and sexual abuse, shaming, withholding affection and attention are behaviours that cut across globally as lousy parenting (Timothy, 2020). According to Mahak (2024), bad parenting encompasses a series of actions that can affect a child psychologically and influence or harm their demeanour, even unintentionally, including inadequate knowledge and a lack of desire to improve in becoming a better parent.

Skosana, Peu, and Mogale (2020), using a phenomenological approach, examined the disconnections and exclusion of parents in the prevention of teenage pregnancy in South Africa; the study asserts that parents have the responsibility of providing the correct information on sex, sex education and postnatal conditions or advice should a pregnancy occur because they are positioned to be role models and coach, hence, education on sexuality must come early. This means

that parents must be informed on the subject matter. Similarly, the findings linked teen pregnancy to inadequate or zero parental guidance, poor communication skills between parents and adolescents, unclear information, lack of mentors and education, parental conflict and perception that providing sex education is more of a risk than preventive. Some parents, due to cultural reasons, find it uncomfortable to discuss sexual education, especially with teenagers, so they push sex education to teachers.

Similarly, Sekinwunga and Whyte (2009), in a qualitative study using focus group discussion, aver that pregnant teen mothers traced their mistakes to parental generation failures due to over-harshness and extreme leniency, coupled with poverty and pressure into early marriage. Mgbokwere, Esienumoh and Uyana (2015), in a descriptive survey on the perception and attitudes of parents toward teenage pregnancy in a rural community in Cross River, observed that 93% of parents' view pregnancy outside marriage as a socially aberrant behaviour, an indication of parental failure, 33% of parent indicated they would disown or send such a child away, 50% of parent said they would end the child's education. Mgbokwere et al. (2009) reveal that there is a gap in their understanding of teen pregnancy management and recommend that parents reinforce their obligation towards their teen daughters to allow them to attain their potentials through the prevention of adolescent pregnancies.

Likewise, Olorunsaiye et al. (2021), in a study on teen pregnancy narrative in Jos, Nigeria, using purposive sampling, assessed factors contributing to teen pregnancy; the study observed that a lack of parent-to-child communication about sexual reproductive health and poor knowledge of contraceptives are major factors identified by one of the respondents who is single and has been pregnant twice, at 15 and 18 years.

Adolescent pregnancy and female multi-partner fertility are permeating global issues with social, economic and security impacts on a nation as it furthers increased school dropout, unemployment, poverty, and increased alcohol and drug use. Dorius and Guzzo (2013) assert that adolescent pregnancy and female multi-partner fertility are major indicators of early sexual activity resulting in unintended pregnancy and teenage drug use and a pointer to adolescents' exposure to poverty, unemployment, and educational disadvantage during the period of birth and throughout childhood. This is depicted in the situation of the protagonist (Jedidah) and her three youngest sons, Shina, a hoodlum and Pere, a pickpocket, who narrowly escaped death (jungle justice) by whiskers when he was almost burnt alive for stealing, and Ejiro a painter who often disguise as a mendicant to beg for alms.

The study examined the management of adolescent pregnancy and female multi-partner fertility in Nigeria via the lens of 'A Tribe Called Judah'. This film, in line with other sources of data, affirms that early sexual debut, the misconception of love among adolescents, poor knowledge of sexual reproductive health, poor parental behaviour, a potential generational failure, and the prevalence of multiple sexual partners have contributed to unplanned pregnancies among adolescent and exacerbates the potential of female multi-partner fertility.

Findings

Five main themes emerge from the findings.

Firstly, while there is no specific data on female multi-partner fertility in Nigeria, however, the conditions and factors that further female multi-partner fertility among the unmarried are prevalent in Nigeria as evidenced in the works of Scholars (Yaya & Bishwajit, 2018; Mgbokwere, et al., 2015; Olorunsaiye, et al. 2022; Folayan, 2014).

Secondly, poor parenting furthered by socio-cultural perception advances the mismanagement of adolescent pregnancy, consequently increasing the potential of female multi-partner fertility among adolescents, as most get pregnant 2-3 years after their first pregnancy, due to anxiety, depression and post-traumatic stress disorder (Olorunsaiye, et al. 2022). The subthemes of the mismanagement of adolescent pregnancy include an increase in school dropouts and an increase in the number of out-of-school children.

Thirdly, the film explores critical gender issues in international relations like teenage pregnancy, gender-based violence, and physical and psychological violence, depicted in the character of Linda (Jedidah's Friend), whose husband not only beats her in public but calls her derogatory name like 'prostitute'. Also is the subject of comprehensive sex education and opportunity for reproductive health care for adolescent girls and teenage mothers, which is a primary goal of international organisations like UNICEF, WHO, Plan International, and UNFPA, amongst others, as well as global efforts at attaining Goal-3 (Ensure Healthy lives and promote wellbeing for all ages) of the Sustainable Development Goal. Proper knowledge of sex education could have prevented Jedidah's first two pregnancies, for idleness and lack of education are factors that cannot be ruled out or contributed to her second pregnancy at 19.

Fourthly, there are socio-cultural factors as an effect of unplanned adolescent pregnancy. On the one hand, religion is subsumed in the enclave of societal norms and values mixed with public expectations (Mgbokwere, et al., 2015). For her father, a clergy felt conflicted as pre-marital sex and pregnancy not only brought shame but contradicted his beliefs and values, which led to the disowning of his daughter. Tribalism and religion are other subthemes that affected her chances of marrying the father of her second child. Another subtheme is the societal perception of a single mother raising children without a father figure; this influenced Jedidiah's fourth relationship, which ended with another child and an absconded father. Then stigmatisation and shame led to depression and excessive alcohol intake as an escape mechanism, culminating in another pregnancy and kidney problems. Therefore, female multi-partner fertility can be unintended, and societal perception plays a major part in the mental health of adolescent mothers, an area most neglected. This affirms Burton's (2011) position that most studies do not examine the underlying factors for female multi-partner fertility.

Fifth is the impact of female multi-partner fertility on the children, an uncertain future and limited opportunities are available, as the teen mother, who is a child, is trying to be a mother and yet a child at the same time. This is even worse in developing countries without a government welfare system. This is visible in the lives of the five sons of the protagonist (Jedidiah): Emeka (35), a sales boy; Adamu (32), a security man; Pere (30), a pickpocket; Shina (27), a hoodlum, and Ejiro (25) an artist, who also impersonate as a beggar. This aligns with the findings of Dorius and Guzzo (2013) on risky behaviours exhibited by children from MPF families and the future outcome of becoming a societal problem.

Conclusion

The management of adolescent pregnancy is a catalyst in the surge of female multi-partner fertility, which has become a global issue. Film is an empirical case study that clarifies concepts and perceptions of events, fitting into the larger societal and cultural dimensions. Early sexual activity increases the likelihood of multi-partner fertility among females, especially among unmarried teen mothers. 'A Tribe Called Judah' correlates with Burton's (2011) assertion that most female multi-partner fertility is unplanned and linked to causal factors related to the role of the male partner. This corresponds with the position of Dr. Jeff Gardere that most multi-partner fertility children are, in reality, growing up without fathers. This calls for more research into multi-partner fertility among adolescents to assess the determinant factors and the specific trigger elements that contribute to the condition and ratio of those growing up without fathers, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa.

Recommendations

1. International organisations like UNICEF, UNFPA and WHO should expand their adolescent programs to cover the girl-child post-natal life.
2. The mental health of teen mothers must be prioritised.
3. Training on the management of adolescent pregnancy should be extended to communities to cover parents and religious institutions, especially in rural areas, as this would help check societal norms and values targeted at sending their pregnant wards away.
4. The national government should encourage and support research in multi-partner fertility due to its capacity to exacerbate social ills, sexually transmitted diseases, and particularly, due to Nigeria's large youth population.

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